

A Study on the Negative Effects of Social Networking Sites (SNSs) On Student's Language in Pakistan

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Abstract:

In the modern era, Online Social Networking Sites (SNSs) have become a major way of communication among the world. The frequent use of social networking sites influence on student's language. The purpose of this study is to examine negative effects of social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter on student's language. This study will measure the frequency of use of these sites and negative effects on language among the different age group of Pakistani students. The study is conducted by using qualitative research. The data will be collect and analysis thorough corpus analysis. The results of the present study will enhance the work conducted on the negative effects of social networks on student's language and encourage researcher for further detailed research in this area

Keywords: Social Networking Sites, Internet, behavior

INTRODUCTION

Social networking is a place where people build social relation to share their ideas, feelings, interests, personal information, pictures, and videos. Facebook, MySpace, Twitter, and Friendster are some social networking sites. The online world has changed dramatically in the last ten years. After the invention of social networking sites, the web became more personal. The attraction of social networking sites has grown constantly, millions of people used the Internet and sign up for the social networking site.

The frequent use of social networking sites effect on student's language. These effects may be positive and negative both but in this paper; we will focus on negative effects of social networking sites. Students use short words, sentences, symbols and improper grammar for fast messaging and saving time but problems arise when students are unable to separate formal language from informal. Here the main problem is for those students who learn language by imitating in speaking and writing; their proficiency may be affected as they imitate improperly. Many types of research have revealed that social networks have negative impacts on students. Language is a necessary tool to communicate with others, but the social networks are affecting student's language rapidly.

Literature Review

Now-a-day's students of colleges and universities use all types of technologies in different aspects of life. As a daily routine, they use Facebook, Twitter, Instagram on their laptops, mobiles, and computers. These social networking sites have some effects on students' language. Facebook is the most used social network by university students, followed by YouTube and Twitter. Moreover, Facebook alone reports that it now has 500 active million users, 50% of whom log on every day. According to Mphahlele & Mashamaite [1], use of short language in text messages is assumed harmful to students' language learning since students mix the text language with the standard or formal language. Consequently, students displayed numerous errors ranging from incorrect spellings to "ungrammatical" sentence constructions. The danger extends to Craig (2003) [2], also found that creates undesirable reading and writing habits due to the common use of abbreviations and unusual jargon, threatens students' literacy because it is thereby damaging students' ability to employ formal literacy skills. In Shih's (2011) [3] interviews with students, he concluded:

...heavily relied on the online correction. When they had no help from the online correction tool, they often used incorrect vocabulary and misspelled words in a regular classroom writing.

Gonzalez (2003) [4] also reported a problem with using online communication:

that it negatively affects the student's use of language, grammar, and spelling. She

suggested that online communication often leads to the use of short phrases and incomplete sentences and that it often becomes an informal conversation that may negatively impact academic writing. Because writing on Facebook is different from writing in a classroom, students might not see the connection between the two forms of writing (academic writing and informal writing). They consider writing on Facebook as a type of informal writing for communication, not for academic purposes.

Selwyn (2009) [5] pointed out that Facebook failed to improve students' writing because students use informal writing structures rather than formal academic writing styles. The most commonly used informal words considered wrong in a formal language that has been widely used on social networking sites are as follows:

1. phonetic spelling use for transcription of standard pronunciations is such as "busy" for "busy," "guyz" for "guys," gonna" for "go" to "luv" for "love." (Dannet & Herrin, 2007, p.97) [6].
2. Capitalization use: all capitals for 'shouting' such as "I SAID NO," asterisks for emphasis such as "the *real* answer" (Crystal, 2001, p. 35) [7].
3. special abbreviations or acronyms used for saving time and making it convenient, such as btw (between), lol/LOL (laughing out loud), btw/BTW (By the way), np/NP (no problem).
4. common shortenings used for easy use and convenience are 'ur' (your), 'i' (I), 'r' (are), 'thx' (thanks), 'pls' (please), f9' (fine).
5. Multiple punctuation marks or letters used for a prosodic effect are such as no more!!!!, Yes!!!!, aaaaahhhh, soooo. (Crystal, 2001, pp. 34-35)
6. emoticons or smileys use for conveying a feeling are such as facing a hard situation -_-!, being happy :) or :-), being sad : (or :- (

The above-mentioned research on negative effect on students' language has given a lot of valuable information, but as they were conducted in a different culture, the generalizability may not be achieved in other cultures. Therefore, the research must be done on different culture language learners.

Statement of problem.

The statement under investigation will "A study on the Negative effects of social networking sites (SNSs) on student's language in Pakistan."

Hypothesis

"The negative effect of social networking sites on students' language"

This study will suppose to answer the following questions:

1. How does the use of social networking sites negative impact on students' language?
2. How slang language effect students' written language?

Objectives of study.

The main objectives of the present study will include followings.

1. To trace out the negative effects of how social networking sites effect on student's formal language.
2. To find out how slang language affects students' written language.

The significance of Study.

The significance of this study is that it would highlight major negative effect on language and give in detail information with reference to the particular area of investigation. It would be helpful to the researchers to explore the remedial measure for these negative impacts. This study would be helpful for students and especially young learners.

Methodology

Population and sampling:

The researcher will select 500 students from public and private universities from Pakistan. Student's age range was from 18 to 25 years. The participants in this study used Facebook, Twitter, and other social networking sites regularly.

Tool or instrument:

Facebook is one of the most popular and widely used social media. Researchers will set up a Facebook account and invite the students to join this account and share the reason. For the selection of students, the researcher will use convenient and random sampling teachinuique

Data collection:

The data will be collected by this social media account and analyzed through corpus analysis. The researcher will ask various questions from the participants who use social networks on a daily basis. Then the data will collect to be analyzed. The study will show that the SNSs have negative effects on students' language which affects their speaking and writing skills.

1. Where did you learn to use informal language?

Only 10% learn from friends and 90% from social network sites.

2. Do you think that use of informal language has a negative effect on your language? Tell me one or more negative effects on your language.

Here 90% population agreed on the statement that it has negative effects on learning a language. 80% told that SNSs effects spelling, 60% on grammar, 20% on vocabulary and 40% on sentence structure.

The graphical representation of the given data is as below:

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the outcome of this research verifies the negative effects of social networking sites on students' language. Previous research works vary according to culture, context and social background. The following research will be based on Pakistani population, where students are confused and unable to distinguish between the formal and informal language.

The following study will explore the negative impact of the use of SNSs in students' language. Since social media plays a crucial role in every aspect of our life, so it is important to pay attention to the use of social media as language learning tool. Research interview results show that many students perceived social network sites (facebook, twitter, Instagram, whatsapp) are an informal platform for learning a language and have negative effects on their academic performance. According to this research results students' often have a problem with grammar structures and vocabulary. This negatively impacts the respondents' proficiency in language learning and effects on their academic performance are high. 90% subject agreed on this statement, and only 10% had a view that they are mature enough and well aware of examination requirements and understand the difference between formal and informal language. According to Kabilan et al. (2010), Omer et al. (2012), Selwyn (2007), and Shih [8] Facebook does not provide a suitable environment for formal language teaching and learning.

References:

- i. Mphahlele M.L. & Mashamaite, K. (2005). *The impact of short message service (sms) language on language proficiency of learners and the sms dictionaries: A challenge for educators and lexicographers. Proceedings of the IADIS International Conference Mobile Learning 2005*, 161.
- ii. Craig, D. (2003). *Instant messaging: The language of youth literacy. The Boothe Prize Essays 2003*, 118-119.
- iii. Shih, R.-C. (2011). *Can Web 2.0 technology assist college students in learning English writing? Integrating Facebook and peer assessment with blended learning. Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 27(5), 829-845.
- iv. Gonzalez, D. (2003). *Teaching and learning through chat: A taxonomy of educational chat for EFL/ESL. Teaching English with Technology*, 3(4), 57-69.
- v. Selwyn, N. (2009) *Faceworking: Exploring students' education-related use of Facebook. Learning, Media and Technology*, 34(2), 157-174.
- vi. Danet, B., & Herring, S. C. (2007). *Multilingualism on the internet. In M. Hellinger & A. Pauwels (Eds.), Language and communication: Diversity and change. Handbook of Applied Linguistics 9 (pp. 553-592). Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.*
- vii. Crystal, D. (2001). *Language and the internet. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.*
- viii. Kabilan, M. K., Ahmad, N., & Abidin, M. J. Z. (2010). *Facebook: An online environment for learning of English in institutions of higher education? The Internet and Higher Education*, 13(4), 179-187.
- ix. Omar, H., Embi, M. A., & Yunus, M. M. (2012). *ESL learners' interaction in an Online discussion via Facebook. Asian Social Science*, 8(11), 67-74.
- x. Selwyn, N. (2007). *The use of computer technology in university teaching and learning: a critical perspective. Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 23(2), 83-94.